
Short Communication

Extraction and Characterization of Castor Seed Oil

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the Extraction and Characterization of Castor Seed Oil, purchased from a local market at Ekwulobia in Anambra State. Vegetable oils have attracted a number of interests in recent years. This is traceable to their vast range of applications in different fields of expertise, especially in their consistent use as industrial additives in our production processes. The oils can be extracted from their sources either by means of mechanical pressure, use of solvent or by leaching. The oil that was considered in this study was extracted by the combination of mechanical pressure and the use of solvent (n-hexane). It was then subjected to characterization into series of physicochemical parameters. The oil sample showed very slight acidic property by indication of 6.8 pH value. The mass, density and specific gravity of the oil were found to be 45.47g, 0.9094 and 0.9203 respectively, showing that the oil is less dense than water. Considering the mass of the seed used during the study (1549.15g), 7.8% yield of the oil expression could be seen as being low. The oil has a viscosity of 9.4250poise and a refractive index of 1.4680; the saponification value was found to be 3.37mg/ml, while the iodine value is 80.58mg/ml. Also, the peroxide value was found to be 14.00mg/ml and the acid value was 11.22mg/ml. The low saponification value of the oil indicates its non-suitability for soap production. However, other parameters as discovered of the sample fall within standard specifications for use in industrial applications.

Keywords: Castor Seed Oil, Extraction, Characterization, Physiochemical Parameters

Received: 19 December 2016

Accepted: 16 May 2017

Introduction

Vegetable oils are triglycerides extracted from plants. Such oils have been part of human culture for millennia. Edible vegetable oils are used in food, both in cooking and as supplements. Many oils, edible and otherwise, are burned as fuel, such as in Oil Lamps and as substitute for petroleum-based fuels. Some of the many other uses of vegetable oils include wood finishing, oil painting and skin care. Vegetable oils can, generally, be classified either by Source (such as castor oil, nut oil, palm oil, and so on) or by Use (such as cooking oil, fuel oil, cosmetic oil, and so on).

Castor-oil plant is a member of the *Euphorbiaceae* family, which is a perennial woody herbaceous plant; its origin is traceable to Egypt, Ethiopia and India (Harborne and Baxter, 2001). Castor oil is derivable from its seed: *Recinus communis* L. (Kleiman, 1990). The uses of castor oil have changed over the years. About sixty years ago, castor was used mainly for medicinal purposes and for general industrial lubricant. But sooner afterwards, Chemical Engineers were able to produce derivatives of the oil that were very beneficial to man. Sulfonated (sulfated) castor oil or Turkey red oil was the first synthetic detergent after many other forms of oils used in soap production became important for leather treatment and industrial lubricants (Elevitch and Manner, 2006). More recently, Chemical Engineers have expanded the uses and applications of castor oil and its derivatives as could be observed in Polymer (Nylon 11) Engineering Plastics, Lubricating Grease, Coatings, Inks, Sealants, Aircraft Lubricants, Surfactants, Emulsion Encapsulants, Plastic Films, Plasticizer (for Coatings), components of Shatterproof Safety Glass and, more importantly, in corrosion inhibition of materials. Castor oil has, also, made its way into the cosmetic industry and other related areas of keen interest due to its non-comedogenicity (that is it does not exacerbate the skin). Obviously, castor oil and its derivatives have become important commodities and, again, a regular topic of interest in the chemical industry.

Generally, there are three principal methods of extracting vegetable oils. The relevant part of the plant may be placed under pressure to extract the oil, giving an expressed oil (manual or mechanical press); oil may be extracted from plants by dissolving parts of the plant in water or another suitable solvent (solvent extraction); the solution may, also, be separated from the plant material and concentrated, giving an extracted oil (leaching). The mixture may then be separated by distilling the solvent away from the oil using appropriate means.

In the present study, which is aimed at extraction and characterization of castor seed oil, a combination of the mechanical press and solvent extraction methods was employed, and the oil and solvent mixture was separated by means of soxhlet extractor.

Materials and Method

Materials Used During the Study

The materials employed to realize the goals of this research work are in three categories, namely: the Sample, the equipment and the reagents. The castor seeds, from which the oil was extracted, were bought at a local market in Ekulobia-Aguatta in Anambra State of Nigeria. The seeds were sun-dried, deshelled and ground into fine powder.

The reagents used include n-hexane, acetic acid, chloroform, de-ionized water, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulfate, starch indicator, diethyl ether, ethanol, phenolphthalein, potassium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid, carbon tetrachloride, Dam's reagent (Wig's iodine) and buffer solution.

Also, the equipment used include pH meter, density bottles, viscometer, beakers, thermostat water bath, conical flasks, pipette, glass stoppers, graduated cylinder, burette, glass rod, stainless bowl, mechanical press machine, soxhlet extractor and centrifuge.

Research Methodology

Oil Extraction: The ground powdered castor seed was impregnated in a solution of n-hexane for 24hours, and the mixture was subjected to mechanical pressure. The solvent-solute mixture was then fed to a soxhlet extractor for 8hours at 60°C, where the solvent was evaporated (distilled) from the oil.

Water Degumming: This is the most popular and ancient method of degumming. Though water degumming is intended to remove hydratable gums, it also removes ether hydrophilic substances such as carbohydrates. The process involved the addition of hot water (2% volume of total oil) to the oil at a temperature 60°C, such that the water and the oil were mixed for 10mins. During the period, the phospholipids absorb the water, thus becoming insoluble in the oil. The insoluble phospholipids inter-combine to form the gum, and the gum was then separated through centrifugation, giving rise to a pure sample of the oil.

Percentage Oil Yield Determination: the percentage yield of the oil is obtained by simple evaluation of the mass of the oil extracted, expressed as the percentage of the mass of the ground solid sample. In order words:

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ISSN: 2141 - 4068 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

$$S.P. = \frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_2 - W_0} = \frac{\text{Mass of Substance}}{\text{Mass of equal Vol. of Water}} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Saponification Value Determination: For the saponification value, 2g of the oil sample was weighed into a conical flask. 25ml of potassium hydroxide was then added, with bumping granulated content; it is constantly stirred and allowed to boil gently for 60mins. A reflux condenser was placed on the flask containing the mixture and was covered in the cork. Few drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added to the warm solution and titrated with 0.5M HCl to the end point, such that the pink colouration of the indicator disappears; the same procedure was used for the blank. The saponification value (S.V.) is given by:

$$S.V. = \frac{56.1 N(V_0 - V_1)}{M} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where V_0 = Vol. of blank solution
 V_1 = Vol. of sample
N = Actual normality of the HCl used
M = Mass of the sample.

Iodine Value Determination: 0.4g of the sample was weighed into a conical flask and 20ml of carbon tetrachloride was added to dissolve the oil. The 25ml of Dam's reagent (Wig's iodine) was then added using a safety pipette. The stopper was inserted and the content of the flask was vigorously swirled. The flask was then placed in the dark for 2hours, 30mins. At the elapse of the time, 20ml of 10% aqueous potassium iodide and 125ml of water were added using a measuring cylinder. The content was then titrated with 0.1M of sodium thiosulphate solution until the yellow colour almost disappeared. At this point, few drops of 1% starch indicator was added and the titration continued by drop-wise addition of more thiosulphate until the blue colour formed disappears (after vigorous shaking). The same procedure was used for the blank test, and the iodine value (I.V.) is given by:

$$I.V. = \frac{12.69 C (V_1 - V_2)}{M} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where C = concentration of sodium thiosulphate used
 V_1 = Vol. of sodium thiosulphate used for blank
 V_2 = Vol. of sodium thiosulphate used for determination
M = Mass of sample.

Peroxide Value Determination: 5g of the sample is weighed into a 250ml glass-stoppered flask. Using a graduated cylinder, 3ml of acetic acid is added to the chloroform solution. The stopper is placed on the flask, and then swirled gently for about 1min., after which 30ml of distilled water is then added and stoppered. The mixture is swirled vigorously to liberate the iodine from the chloroform layer. The mixture is then titrated with 0.1N sodium thiosulphate, in the presence of starch indicator, until blue-gray colour disappears in aqueous upper layer. The peroxide value is evaluated as follows:

$$P.V. = (S - B)N \times 200 \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where: S = titre value of sample
B = titre value of blank
N = normality of the thiosulphate

Acid Value Determination: 25ml of diethyl ether and 25ml ethanol in were mixed a 250ml beaker. The resulting mixture was added to 10g of the oil in a 250ml conical flask, with the addition of few drops of phenolphthalein. The mixture was then titrated with 0.1M Of sodium hydroxide and shaken consistently. The end point is indicated by a dark-pink colouration. The Acid Value is given by:

$$Acid\ Value = \frac{56.9\ M\ V}{m} \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Where: m = mass of sample used
M = Molarity of the Base (NaOH)
V = titre value

From which the Free Fatty Acid Value can be evaluated as follows:

$$Free\ Fatty\ Acid\ Value = \frac{Acid\ Value}{2} \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Results and Discussion

The results of the sample characterization, based on its physiochemical parameters, are presented in Table 1 while details of the computations that generated the results are placed at the appendix for free data flow.

The sample gave a percentage oil yield of 7.8; this could be considered as being low compared to some other vegetable oils like groundnut oil, and is traceable to woody/herbaceous nature of the source which has the capacity of lowering the triglyceride properties. The potential hydrogen value of 6.8 shows that the oil sample is slightly acidic, and this agrees with tolerable acidic composition of edible oils as reviewed by Dakia *et al* (2007). The mass, density and specific gravity of the oil sample were found to be 45.47g, 0.9094 and 0.9203 respectively. This indicates that the oil is less dense than water and may likely be devoid of heavy metals.

Table 1: Characterization on the Physiochemical Properties of the Oil Sample

S/N	PARAMETER	RESULTS
1	Percentage Oil Yield (%)	7.8
2	Potential Hydrogen, pH	6.8
3	Mass of oil (g)	45.47
4	Density (g/ml)	0.9094
5	Specific Gravity	0.9203
6	Viscosity (Pois)	9.4250
7	Refractive Index	1.4680
8	Saponification Value (mg/ml)	3.37
9	Iodine Value (mg/ml)	80.58
10	Peroxide Value (mg/ml)	14.00
11	Acid Value (mg/ml)	11.22
12	Free Fatty Acid (mg/ml)	5.61

The oil has a viscosity of 9.4250poise, and this is within the viscosity range of other organic oils such as rubber seed oil, shear butter oil and crambe oil (Asuquo *et al*, 2012a; Asuquo *et al*, 2010). The refractive index was found to be 1.4680; this result conforms to

the stipulations of Kovo and Bawa (2007) that the refractive index of organic oils falls between 1.3 and 1.6.

Also, the sample has a saponification of 3.37mg/ml; this is very low, compared with those of other organic oils (187-198mg/ml), such as soybean, peanut and cotton seed oil (Kleiman, 1990). This goes a long way to explain the non-suitability of the oil for soap production. Asuquo *et al* (2012b) documented that the lower the saponification value of an oil sample, the lower its lauric acid content. According to the report, the lauric acid content and the saponification value oil serve as important parameters in determining the suitability of the oil for soap making. The iodine value of 89.58mg/ml obtained in this study is lower than that obtained for rubber seed oil in Asuquo *et al* (2012a), which indicates that the oil sample under study is less unsaturated than the rubber seed oil. According to Elevitch and manner (2006), the iodine value measures the degree of unsaturation in a vegetable oil sample. The report reviews that the iodine value determines the stability of the oil to oxidation, and allows the overall unsaturation of the fat to be determined qualitatively. The peroxide and acid values were identified to be 14.00mg/ml and 11.22mg/ml respectively; these all fall within the standard range for organic acids. However, acid values can vary from one oil sample to another based on the method of extraction employed, with high acidity for soxhlet extraction techniques due to the onset of oxidation.

Conclusion

The present study was anchored on the extraction of vegetable oil from castor seed, and the subsequent characterization of its physiochemical parameters. Considering the mass of the solid invested into the extraction process, the percentage yield of the oil could be identified to have been low. The oil extract was, also, discovered to possess a very low saponification value when compared with most organic oils, and as such is not recommendable for soap production. However, other parameters agreed with the standard stipulations and as such makes the oil sample appropriate for environmental-friendly applications.

References

- Asuquo J.E., Anusiem A.C.I. and Etim E.E. (2012a). Extraction and Characterization of Rubber Seed Oil. *International Journal of Modern Chemistry*, 1(3): 109-115.
- Asuquo J.E., Anusiem A.C.I. and Etim E.E. (2012b). Comparative Study of the Effect of Temperature on the Adsorption of Metallic Soaps of Shear Butter, Castor Oil and Rubber Seed Oil onto Hematite. *International Journal of Modern Chemistry*, 3(1): 39-50.
- Asuquo J.E., Anusiem A.C.I. and Etim E.E. (2010). Extraction and Characterization of Shear Butter Oil. *World Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(1): 282-288.
- Dakia P.A., Wathelet B., and Paquot M. (2007). Isolation and Chemical Evaluation of Carob (*Ceratonia siliqua L.*) Seed Germ. *Journal of Food Chemistry*, 102(4): 1368-1374.
- Elevitch C.R. and Manner H.I. (2006). Traditional Trees of Pacific Islands: their Culture, Environment and Uses. *Journal of Food Chemistry*, 91(4): 723-729.
- Harborne J.B. and Baxter H. (2001). Chemical Dictionary of Economic Plants; *John Wiley and Sons*, New York.
- Kleiman R. (1990). Chemistry of New Industrial Oil Seed Crops. In: J. Janick and J.E. Simon (eds.). *Advances in New Crops*; Timber Press, Portland; pp 196-203.